

THE SIGNIFICANCE AND USAGE OF INTEGRATED SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

Xadicha Shuhratova

Scientific advisers: Khan Tatyana

Ivan Berejnov

Student, English Education,

Kimyo International University in Tashkent

e-mail: shuhratovaxadicha@gmail.com,

+998909848104

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10851948>

Abstract

Why do we need to include integrated skills in our lesson? How can it be important? This method not only encourages greater comprehension, increased competency, and increased motivation, but it also accurately represents language use in everyday situations. We explore the real-world application of integrated skills, providing instructional approaches, exercises, and materials that logically connect the four linguistic pillars. We provide examples of how teachers might plan engaging learning activities that cut across skill barriers, such as group projects and technology-driven assignments. This article emphasizes the value of including integrated skills in teaching English and how adopting this strategy gives students the skills they need to become confident, adaptable communicators who can successfully negotiate the ever-changing language landscape.

Keywords: Integrated skills, English language teaching, communication, real-world relevance, learner motivation, teaching strategies, technology

Introduction

Using speaking, writing, listening, and reading as well as other fundamental language abilities freshly and engagingly is known as integrated skills. By providing children with ongoing practice, teaching with integrated skills aims to improve their general social and academic communication abilities while introducing them to a fresh and engaging subject.

According to Oxford (2001), the notion of a tapestry is presented; it is composed of four talents in addition to the teacher, student, environment, and pertinent languages. As in a genuine tapestry, where parallel threads are not touching, supporting, or interacting with one another, she thought that the lack of such threads may result in isolated, segregated skills. Moreover, she makes the case that teaching integrated language skills encompasses connected or related skills including proficiency with vocabulary, spelling, pronunciation, grammar, meaning, and usage. This creates an integrated approach to language instruction, in her opinion.

Language teaching. Listening

According to Brown and Yule (1983), listening is a difficult task not only because of the intricacy of the process itself but also because of the characteristics of the speaker, the listener, the message's substance, and any accompanying visual aids. Boosts Interaction in the Real World: Language acquisition is a process. You may replicate how communication occurs in real life by including language, speaking, and writing tasks with listening ones. Pupils get a more comprehensive comprehension and get ready to use the language actively by connecting what they hear to other skills. Increases Understanding and Memory: Comprehending music on

numerous levels is strengthened by the integration of other talents. Analyzing and applying critical thinking skills is encouraged when discussing with peers about the recording. Assignments that require students to analyze and synthesize what they have heard help them strengthen their understanding. Greater learning and retention are the results of this multifaceted strategy. Offers Differentiated Instruction: By including skills, you can accommodate a range of learning preferences. Kinesthetic learners can act out sections of the story, while visual learners can draw diagrams or images based on the audio. All students will be able to interact meaningfully with the content thanks to this differentiation.

Examples of Integration:

Listen to a podcast on a historical event, then write a newspaper article reporting it.

Watch a video interview, then discuss the speaker's opinions and provide counter-arguments.

Listen to a song, then analyze the lyrics and create a visual representation of them.

Picture 1

Speaking.

Speaking has long been seen as unimportant, and English language instructors have taught speaking mostly as drills or dialogue memorization. The modern environment demands that the aim of instruction Speaking should help students become more proficient communicators because it is the only method for them to express themselves and learn how to abide by the social and cultural norms that are appropriate in each communication situation. The following categories can be utilized to represent how students should progress in their speaking abilities in the classroom (Brown, 2001): A relatively small amount of speaking time in the classroom may be imitative. Genuinely be speech-generating "human tape recorder speech," in which students attempt to isolate a certain vowel sound or rehearse a tone contour. Such imitation serves the goal of concentrating on a certain linguistic form element rather than fostering meaningful engagement. Intensive speaking- is speaking in a way that goes beyond imitation and incorporates any speaking exercises meant to train specific phonological or grammatical

skills. Responses - are brief and come in response to queries or remarks posed by the teacher or students. A discussion that is conducted for transactional language. An expanded version of responsive language- is used to communicate or exchange specialized information. The primary objective of interpersonal communication, or discourse, was to uphold social connections rather than convey facts and information. A casual register, colloquial language, emotionally charged language, slang, and sarcasm are some of the elements that make these interactions a little more challenging for learners. Comprehensive (monolog): In this case, the register is more deliberate and formal. It may be prearranged or spontaneous. Intermediate and advanced students are expected to provide lengthy monologues in the form of oral reports that may be brief speeches summarized.

Picture 2

Writing.

Writing helps students acquire language more quickly because it allows them to practice using words, phrases, and longer writing pieces to express themselves clearly and reinforce the grammar and vocabulary they are learning in class (Bello, 1997). The ability to construct sentences is not the sole skill required for communication, as noted by Widdowson (1972). By using phrases to carry out a range of distinct tasks that are fundamentally social in character, we engage in communication. The Approach of Free-Writing.

Instead of focusing on form, this method stresses content and fluency. Teachers that use this method typically invite their pupils to write freely on a without giving attention to spelling and punctuation. Using a Process Approach

This method places more focus on the writing process than the final output.

Writing a first draft and getting reader feedback, which will include suggestions for fresh concepts, fresh phrases, and new vocabulary; a first draft revision; and lastly, a second draft and the finished work. Many teachers give their students the chance to thoroughly investigate a topic through prewriting exercises like brainstorming, reading, and debating before assigning them to write about it. During a brainstorming session, words, phrases, or ideas are generated without regard for their appropriateness, correctness, or sequence. New concepts are produced when later links are established between them. One can brainstorm separately on paper or aloud in class or in a group.

Picture 3

Reading.

One of the fundamental abilities is reading, and becoming literate is a crucial educational objective. For those learning a foreign language, reading offers several chances. The ability to read enables students to learn new vocabulary, acquire new experiences, and expand their knowledge. Reading provides readers with the opportunity to enjoy literature, which satisfies their cultural and aesthetic demands as well as their cognitive and psychological needs to learn, comprehend, and study. The process of reading is complex and includes the following components: the ability of the learner to identify the major concepts of the target text; the ability of the learner to understand the text as a whole; and the ability of the learner to associate graphical and phonetic language systems. Pre-, during-, and post-reading activities are the

three key steps that make up the entire reading experience. Different exercises and learning assignments may be included in each of these three phases. During the pre-reading phase, educators can motivate students through various activities that enhance their learning motivation, expand their vocabulary, and pique the class's attention prior to the reading process. Making predictions about the content, setting goals and objectives for reading, talking about students' experiences and background with the subject, playing vocabulary games, scaffolding (which aids in understanding the reading theme), and becoming familiar with unfamiliar words are a few examples of activities that can be done. The second step involves reading the material aloud and taking notes. It might also involve organizing the text's primary ideas logically, tracking previously mentioned objectives, posing questions to the text and researching possible answers, and keeping a log of the activities.

References:

1. Download citation of THE IMPORTANCE OF INTEGRATING READING AND WRITING FOR THE EFL TEACHING. (n.d.). ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326266995_THE_IMPORTANCE_OF_INTEGRATING_READING_AND_WRITING_FOR_THE_EFL_TEACHING/citation/download
2. Pysarchyk, O. L., & Yamshynska, N. V. (2015). THE IMPORTANCE OF INTEGRATING READING AND WRITING FOR THE EFL TEACHING. *Advanced Education*, 0(3), 77–83. <https://doi.org/10.20535/2410-8286.44298>
3. View of the importance of integrated skills in teaching English as a foreign language | FAN, TA'LIM VA AMALIYOTNING INTEGRASIYASI. (n.d.). <https://journal.bilig.uz/isepsmj/article/view/106/98>
4. View of THE IMPORTANCE OF INTEGRATED SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR EFL LEARNERS. (n.d.). <https://newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/4021/3812>
5. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. (n.d.). <https://univerpubl.com/index.php/semantic>
6. https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.researchgate.net%2Ffigure%2FThe-Teaching-Speaking-Cycle_fig1_359025138&psig=AOvVaw30r1ixAzt0ze01pZ-NVuE3&ust=1707452896557000&source=images&cd=vfe&opi=89978449&ved=0CBQQjhxqFwoTCKiarN7xmoQDFQAAAAAdAAAAABAE
7. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Frajanurunnadiah.wordpress.com%2F2010%2F04%2F26%2Ftypes-of-listening%2F&psig=AOvVaw2bXsVgDQoIIAGxH76RLs53&ust=1707452593477000&source=images&cd=vfe&opi=89978449&ved=0CAUQjB1qFwoTCPiC9c3wmoQDFQAAAAAdAAAAABAI>
8. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Ffealdaylight.wordpress.com%2F2019%2F01%2F15%2Fwhy-we-should-model-and-teach-the-writing-process-to-our-eal-learners%2F&psig=AOvVaw0DxnD9Lhbs0VCYhZsKEJWB&ust=1707453026036000&source=images&cd=vfe&opi=89978449&ved=0CBQQjhxqFwoTCJCB-pvymoQDFQAAAAAdAAAAABAT>